

Crux: Symbolic Execution Meets SMT-based Verification (Competition Contribution)

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Abstract. CRUX is a software verification tool that proves properties of imperative programs containing inline specifications. CRUX translates programs into functional models that can be reasoned about in a symbolic execution engine, which ultimately uses SMT solvers to discharge proof obligations. There are several frontends to CRUX, but the C frontend, CRUX-LLVM, is the most mature at present.

Keywords: Verification · Symbolic execution · SMT

1 Verification Approach

CRUX [5] is a verification tool for C and other imperative languages that is built on top of CRUCIBLE [2], a general-purpose symbolic execution engine. CRUCIBLE works by taking an imperative program with clear termination conditions and converting it to a functional model [3]. Once code is extracted into a functional model, it can be checked to see if it upholds properties of interest.

CRUCIBLE makes use of symbolic formulas written in the WHAT4 library [4]. WHAT4 provides a common abstraction over the many features that various SMT solvers offer. When CRUCIBLE verifies goals, it will sometimes discharge proof obligations by converting the corresponding WHAT4 formulas to SMT queries and handing them to an appropriate solver. To decrease the search space that solvers must consider, CRUCIBLE will also apply simplification rules to its WHAT4 formulas to keep them as compact as possible.

In contrast to other implementations of symbolic execution, which model the symbolic state of each individual path in a program, CRUCIBLE generates a single model for a whole program's state. This enables representing the entire semantics of a program. In order to represent control-flow branches in a program, CRUCIBLE uses a technique called *path merging*. When symbolic execution of two different paths reaches a node that post-dominates all nodes in both paths, CRUCIBLE will merge the two paths' states into a single symbolic state.

Fig. 1. The architecture of CRUX-LLVM.

2 Software Architecture

CRUX is implemented in Haskell. CRUX’s flagship frontend is CRUX-LLVM, which leverages LLVM to verify single-threaded C and C++ code. There are also experimental frontends for Java, Rust, and concurrent programs [1]. For the competition, only the C frontend is used.

The architecture of CRUX-LLVM is pictured in Figure 1. CRUX-LLVM works by first using Clang to compile a source file to LLVM bitcode, parsing the resulting bitcode using a custom Haskell-based parser, and then translating the bitcode into a CRUCIBLE control-flow graph. CRUX supports using different SMT solvers to solve proof goals, including Boolector, CVC4, dReal, STP, Yices, and Z3.

3 Discussion of Strengths and Weaknesses of the Approach

Because CRUX models the entire symbolic state of a program, it performs best on programs with clear termination criteria. The *NoOverflow* category largely consists of such programs, and as such, CRUX performs quite well in that category. Programs with non-obvious termination conditions, such as programs with `for` loops with symbolic iteration bounds, give CRUX more trouble. Under its default settings, CRUX will often fail to terminate on such loops; however, termination can be forced by bounding loops or via timeouts. When termination is forced in this way, CRUX cannot verify programs, but may still be able to find errors. Unlike some systems, CRUX makes no attempt to infer loop invariants. Many programs in the *SoftwareSystems* category, and some in *ReachSafety*, have non-obvious termination conditions or are explicitly written as non-terminating reactive loop programs. Thus, CRUX fares less well there.

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Our philosophy when developing CRUX-LLVM has been to strictly handle undefined behavior and other situations not fully specified by the C standards. As such, the default behavior of CRUX-LLVM is to treat reads from uninitialized memory as program errors and to always produce verification conditions relating to memory safety, overflow, etc. However, many of the benchmark programs will freely read from uninitialized memory, and a few contain undefined behaviors that are unrelated to the class of error the benchmark is intended to exercise. To mitigate this we have added options to CRUX-LLVM for, e.g., specifying that uninterpreted bytes should be returned for uninitialized reads instead of producing verification errors. Still, CRUX-LLVM currently produces quite a few “false” negative results in the benchmark suite. This should give us plenty of work to do in our post-mortem investigations. We are very pleased to note good results in the soundness direction, however; CRUX-LLVM reports only one false positive result among the benchmarks we exercised (the cause for which we are still investigating).

The witness automata that CRUX generates currently are rather suboptimal. For correct programs, CRUX will generate a trivial correctness witness with a single node. As CRUX does not infer loop invariants or function specifications, it is unclear what information should be provided to the witness checkers. CRUX, however, is somewhat better at generating violation witnesses. For these, it will generate a straight-line path of nodes, where each edge transitions to the head of a basic block in the LLVM bitcode until reaching the property violation. This approach works reasonably well on many programs, although there are still quite a few programs for which this approach fails. This is likely because CRUX’s violation witnesses only include line numbers at present. We suspect that including additional program state information (e.g., the concrete values of function arguments) will improve this situation.

4 Tool Setup and Configuration

The competition contribution is based on CRUX version 0.5³. Additionally, the contribution makes use of version 12.0.0 of the LLVM toolchain and version 4.8.7 of Z3. The contribution also bundles version 2.6.2 of Yices, although Z3 is the only solver used during the competition in practice.

CRUX participated in the *ReachSafety*, *NoOverflows*, and *SoftwareSystems* categories (while opting out from *SoftwareSystems-*-MemSafety*). CRUX’s tool-info module and the benchmark definition for SV-COMP are both named `crux`. They correspond to invoking CRUX as follows:

```
crux-llvm-svcomp-driver.sh
  --svcomp-spec <property>.prp --svcomp-arch <32bit|64bit>
  input.c
```

Note that `crux-llvm-svcomp-driver.sh` is a small script that invokes the `crux-llvm` binary with the appropriate LLVM tools and SMT solvers added

³ <https://github.com/GaloisInc/crucible/releases/tag/crux-v0.5>

to the PATH. The script also reads the `<property>.prp` file to determine which CRUX-specific configuration file to pass to `crux-llvm`. For example, if the script is given a `.prp` file containing the property used in the *ReachSafety* category, then the script will pass an `unreach-call.config` file for `crux-llvm` that instructs it to check if the designated error function is reached and to ignore other classes of errors (e.g., overflow).

5 Software Project and Contributors

CRUX is maintained by Galois, Inc. with various contributors. Binary distributions of CRUX are available on Galois' web page ⁴, and the source code is available on GitHub ⁵ under the 3-Clause BSD License.

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⁴ <https://crux.galois.com>

⁵ <https://github.com/GaloisInc/crucible>